

Life of a data archive: Workflow, staff, skills, partnerships

ADP example

Irena Vipavc Brvar, ADP

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Data life cycle – CREATING DATA

- Start proper research data management planning early.
- Workshops on RDM; on consent form and other ethical obligations / Open Data.
- ADP's collection of questionnaires and other materials useful for new surveys (export in DDI possible – direct use in survey tools – Blaise, *1ka*).

Data life cycle – PROCESSING DATA

- Provide guidelines on Data file (formats, organizations, storage).
- Guidance on Anonymisation and tools
- Which accompanying materials to save and how.
- Temporary university repository (UL, MB, UP).
- Inclusion in study process – lectures about processing of data.

Open Science Slovenia (www.openscience.si)

- similar content detection,
- federated search,
- recommendation system.

enable deposit and preservation of electronic versions of diploma, master and doctoral theses, of publications of the universities' employees as well as of **research data**

Compliance with [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#).

[The fulfilment of obligatory open access to all publications](#) from projects in Horizon 2020. Connected with [COBISS.SI](#) and [SICRIS](#), included into [DART-Europe portal](#) and different directories, aggregators and search engines ([OpenDOAR](#), [ROAR](#), [BASE](#) ...).

Data life cycle – ANALYSING DATA

- Offer guidance if necessary.
- In some occasions involved in data analysing as well.
- Relationship with librarians and editors of scientific journals.

Data life cycle – PRESERVING DATA

- Protocols for data deposit and archiving at ADP.
- Correct metadata (documentation and data saved in proper format, necessary metadata documentation – use of standards (DDI) and tools.
- Workshops for depositors.
- ADP being designated repository for social science data (defined by Slovene Research Agency)

SERVICE FOR DATA DEPOSITORS

Counselling, guidelines, tools such as Metadata editor, processing and preparation of acquisition

DDI Metadata Editor (Nesstar Publisher)

The IHSN Metadata Editor, also known as the Nesstar Publisher, is a specialized XML editor compliant with the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) 2.n and the Dublin Core metadata standards

Number	Name	Label	Width	StartCol	EndCol
v7	w2_a_intv_m	a14_m - Date of interview	2	21	22
v8	w2_a_intv_y	a14_y - Date of interview	4	23	26
v9	w2_a_intvart	a15 - Interview start time	4	27	30
v10	w2_a_refusal	a22 - Reason for refusal	2	31	32
v11	w2_a_refint	a23 - Degree of interact	2	33	34
v12	w2_a_dob_m	b1_m - Date of birth (m)	2	35	36
v13	w2_a_dob_y	b1_y - Date of birth (y)	4	37	40
v14	w2_a_gen	b2 - Gender	2	41	42

OBRAZEC ZA OPIS RAZISKAVE

Pričujoči obrazec temelji na vsebinskih opredelitvah iz mednarodnega Standardnega opisa raziskave (<http://www.icpsr.umich.edu/DDI/>). Izpolnjujete lahko s pomočjo navadnega urejevalnika besedila. Cel dokument je razdeljen na štiri osnovna poglavja: opis vsebine raziskave, opis datotek, opis spremljajočega gradiva. Pričujoči Obrazec je namenjen predvsem opisu prvega poglavja. Priporočamo, da se pri izpolnjevanju zgljedujete pri domačih že zaključenih opisih raziskav v XML <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opis/index.xml>.

Možno je tudi direktno izpolnjevanje XML dokumenta, za kar potrebujete poseben urejevalnik besedila, ki to podpira. Ta postopek je zelo primeren za raziskave v seriji, kjer je potrebnih le malo popravkov in lahko za osnovo vzamemo opis predhodne raziskave. V kolikor se za to odločite, vam v ADP nudimo vso potrebno pomoč.

Opis raziskave naj bo narejen tako v slovenskem kot angleškem jeziku.

Opis raziskave <studyDesc>

Naslov, avtor, izdelava in distribucija <citation>

<pbSmt>
Naslov Zabeležite naslov raziskave. Npr. *Slovensko javno mnenje 1999/4* <tit>

</tit>
Podnaslov Zabeležite podnaslov raziskave. Npr. *Stališča o pridruženju Evropski Uniji* <subTit>

</subTit>
Naslov v drugem jeziku Naslov v angleškem jeziku. V kolikor je originalni naslov v tujem jeziku navedite tudi tega. Npr. *Slovene Public Opinion Survey 1999/4 : Attitudes on Integration in the European Union* <parTit>

Odgovornost <rspSmt>

- Service provider – infrastructural center
- Evaluation of received materials
- Bibliographic reference

Bibliografije raziskovalcev

Personal Bibliographies

2.20 Complete scientific database or corpus

40. ADAM, Frane, KRISTAN, Primož, VOJVODIČ, Ana, RONČEVIČ, Borut, KALČIČ, Špela, PODMENIK, Dane, LAMUT, Urša, BESEDNJAK VALIČ, Tamara. *RAZJED10 - Lokalna in regionalna razvojna jedra = [Local and regional developmental cores] : [datoteka podatkov]*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov, [2010].

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/razjed10/>. [COBISS.SI-ID [29428061](#)]

kategorija: 2H (Z2), tipologijo je verificiral OSICD

točke: 3.75, št. avtorjev: 8

41. MAKAROVIČ, Matej, RONČEVIČ, Borut, TOMŠIČ, Matevž, BESEDNJAK VALIČ, Tamara. *Slovenski utrip 1/2010 : družba znanja*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov, 2010. <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/sutr1001/>. [COBISS.SI-ID [1024194881](#)]

kategorija: 2H (Z2); tipologijo je verificiral OSICD

točke: 7.5, št. avtorjev: 4

- Potential expansion to areas that are far less represented, including Quali-data, ethnology, economics, pedagogy, psychology etc.

INTERNAL SERVICE: DIGITAL PRESERVATION

- DEVELOPMENT OF APPLICATION ON THE TOP OF FEDORA
- PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER (URN)
- USING SECOND LOCATION (ARNES)
- CERTIFICATION (DSA) AND INCLUSION IN REPOSITORIES

THOMSON REUTERS

Controlled Vocabularies

DDI-Codebook

The current version of DDI-C is [2.5](#).

DDI-Lifecycle

[DDI 3.1](#)

Data life cycle – GIVING ACCESS TO DATA

- Protocols for accessing data.
- Licences.
- Making data available – repository – open data rules – H2020.

Data life cycle – RE-USING DATA

SERVICES FOR DATA USERS

Viewing and browsing data and documentation of surveys

Slovenian Public Opinion 2010: European Social Survey

Study description Data description Materials and publications Download data

ADP - IDNo: SJM10

Main author(s):

Kurdija, Slavko
Malnar, Brina
Uhan, Samo
Hafner-Fink, Mitja
Štebe, Janez

Other co-workers >

Producer:

CJM - Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre (Ljubljana, Slovenia; 2011)

Funding agency:

Agencija za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije = Slovenian Research Agency

Series:

- *SJM/Slovensko javno mnenje = Slovene Public Opinion Survey*
The SJM survey closely resemble the type of a General Social Surveys known in other countries. Its aim is to provide the scientific community with the data about changes in subjective perceptions and attitudes of the general population. The topics which repeats from year to year beginning with 1968 are the evaluations of general and economic situation in society, interethnic relations in Slovenia and Yugoslavia, politics, ecology and religion. Beginning in 1989 a SJM survey adds a cross-national comparative perspective by adopting and replicating some of the most well-known international comparative surveys, regional Central and East European as well as global. Occasionally under the SJM title appears some specialised topical projects.

- *ESS/European Social Survey*
The European Social Survey (ESS) is a multi-country survey covering over 20 nations. Its aim is to chart and explain the interaction between Europe's changing institutions and populations. The

DATA CATALOG

Complete study description

Access to data:

study description | download data

Status of the study: 4 - Full Study XML DDI Codebook Data description text.

9: highest range, comparative research, influential population methodological excellence
Publication date: 2012

How to quote this study?

Kurdija, Slavko, Brina Malnar, Mitja Hafner-Fink and Janez Štebe. Opinion 2010: European Social Survey. Ljubljana: Univerza na Ljubljani, Fakulteta za družbene vede = Faculty of Social Sciences, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre, 2011. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza na Ljubljani, Arhiv podatkov = Social Science [distribution], 2012.

DESCRIPTION TABULATION ANALYSIS

Dataset: [SJM082]³ Slovene Public Opinion 2008/2 : European social survey

Full Title
[SJM082]³ Slovene Public Opinion 2008/2 : European social survey

Subtitle
European social survey

Parallel Title
Slovensko javno mnenje 2008/2. Evropska družboslovna raziskava

Identification Number
sjm082-en

Authoring Entity

- Kurdija Slavko Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Malnar, Brina Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Hafner Fink, Mitja Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Uhan, Samo Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Štebe, Janez Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij

Other identifications and acknowledgments

- Toš, Niko Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij

DESCRIPTION TABULATION ANALYSIS

Dataset: [SJM10-en]³ Slovenian Public Opinion 2010

Variable G1 : Bil sem vesel in dobre volje.

PreQuestion Text

Prebral vam bom nekaj izjav o tem, kako se morda počutite v zadnjem času. Za vsako posebej povejte, kako pogosto ste se tako počutili v zadnjih dveh tednih.

Literal Question

G1 Bil sem vesel in dobre volje.

Values	Categories	N	
1	ves čas	140	10.0%
2	večino časa	574	41.1%
3	več kot polovico časa	406	29.0%
4	manj kot polovico časa	156	11.2%
5	le malo časa	111	7.9%
6	nikoli	11	0.8%
8	ne vem	3	
9	b.o.	2	

Summary Statistics

Valid cases	1398
Missing cases	5
Minimum	1
Maximum	6.0

This variable is numeric

SERVICES FOR DATA USERS

Easy online registration

SEARCH

Search criteria: [Help](#)

Study Descripti Study Description

Geographic Coverage
Geographic Unit
Unit of Analysis
Universe
Kind of Data
Methodology and Processing
Data Collection Methodology
Time Method
Sampling Procedure
Mode of Data Collection
Weighting
Data Access
Data Use Statement
Location
Variable Description
Variable Name
Question Text
Variable Label
Variable Concept
Category Label

More Less

Return what?

Search for datasets
 Search for variables
 Search for tables

Search

Registration to access data

Dear users!
Please, complete the registration form below.
After confirmation you will receive username and password on your email.
Additional information is available in *Help with completing the registration form and Materials on demand*.

Help with completing the registration form
Materials on demand
Forgot your password?

Fields marked with * are required.

First name*:

Last name*:

Address*:

Postcode and city*:

User category*:

Organization

Taxpayer Yes

VAT number

Telephone:

Fax:

Email address*:

Select purpose of the use of material. You can choose between *educational*, *scientific*, *commercial* and *public* purpose.

Purpose of the use*:

Select how you are going to use the material. You can choose between *online data analysis* or *downloading data*. In the latter case you have to analyse data in a suitable statistical program.

I will*:

Please, specify the purpose of the use*:

(150 to 500 characters)

Help desk with several manuals published on-line

Workshops and presence at conferences and summer schools

Partnership with similar institutions

ADP work in short

- Involvement in scientific communities (define rules for researchers at the UNI level; work closely with editors of scientific journals to define open data and citation policy; preparing national action plan (Štebe, 2013)).
- Help researchers with their research in order to have less work later.
- Processing data (preparation for long term preservation and secondary usage).
- Promote use.
- Work closely with other CESSDA archives.

OAIS MODEL in ADP

ADP staff /skills

Head of ADP (part time lecturer)

5 experts (1 for NSI, 1 for communication, 1 project manager, 2 acquisition and producer support)

1-2 students

Outsourcing IT

SKILLS:

- statistics, methodology, computer science,
- social informatics / data librarian
- Journalism, communication strategy.
- MS office, XML editor, statistical package (SPSS, STATA, R)
- Social media skills (publishing on web, blog, twitter, etc.)

Sources mentioned

- UKDA – Create & Manage Data: Research Data Lifecycle [<http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage/life-cycle>, 2.5.2015]
- Milan Ojsteršek, Janez Brezovnik, Mojca Kotar, Marko Ferme, Goran Hrovat, Albin Bregant, Mladen Borovič, (2014) "Establishing of a Slovenian open access infrastructure: a technical point of view", Program: electronic library and information systems, Vol. 48 Iss: 4, pp.394-412. [<http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/PROG-02-2014-0005>, 2.5.2015]
- Štebe, Janez, Sonja Bezjak and Irena Vipavc Brvar (2015): Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Založba FDV. [<URN:NBN:SI:DOC-GODPXMZ1>, 2.5.2015]
- Štebe, Janez, Sonja Bezjak and Sanja Lužar (2013): Odprti podatki. Načrt za vzpostavitev sistema odprtega dostopa do raziskovalnih podatkov v Sloveniji [OPEN DATA – Action Plan for the Establishment of a System of Open Access to Publicly Funded Research Data in Slovenia]. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Založba FDV. [<URN:NBN:SI:DOC-US3XRRB2>, 2.5.2015]